

**SEMNIFICAȚIILE TERMENULUI „INFRAȚIUNE” ÎN ROMÂNĂ
ȘI RUSĂ, ȘI IMPACTUL LOR ASUPRA SISTEMELOR JURIDIC
ȘI SOCIAL ALE REPUBLICII MOLDOVA /**

**THE MEANINGS OF THE TERM "INFRAȚIUNE" IN ROMANIAN
AND RUSSIAN, AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE LEGAL
AND SOCIAL SYSTEMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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This research explores the terminological meaning of the Romanian word "infrațione" through a multi-faceted analysis, including linguistic, legal and sociological perspectives. The study highlights the historical evolution of the term, its use in different fields and the impact on the legal system and society. The legal interpretation of the term "infrațione" in the legal norms of the Republic of Moldova and the impact of translation on applicability and perception.